

Catalytic Vapour Phase Oxidation of Anthracene to Anthraquinone

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An earlier paper presented at the symposium on catalysis held at Banaras Hindu University in 1973 had highlighted the work done at the Central Fuel Research Institute on the vapour phase oxidation of anthracene to anthraquinone in the fluid bed. Subsequent work has resulted in the development of catalysts with much superior performance. It has been found that fused catalysts of the type $V_2O_5-K_2O-H_2SO_4-SiO_2$ are particularly efficient for the vapour phase oxidation of anthracene to anthraquinone. The optimum composition has been found to give consistent conversion of over 99% anthracene at a selectivity level of 93% to anthraquinone in the temperature range 350-410° at contact times in the order of 0.3 to 0.4 seconds. A particularly desirable feature of the catalyst was its ability to maintain high yields at space velocities of anthracene feed up to 235 gms per hour per litre of catalyst. The products of oxidation after removal of water soluble phthalic and maleic anhydride consist of more than 99% anthraquinone. The effect of variation of composition of catalyst, space velocity of feed and reaction temperature have been studied and discussed in this paper.

WORK on the development of catalysts and processes for the oxidation of anthracene to anthraquinone has been in progress at the CFRI for quite some time. The work done earlier has already formed the basis for a number of publications and patents¹⁻⁵. The present study concerns further work done on the development of a selective catalyst for the vapour phase oxidation of anthracene to anthraquinone under fluidized bed conditions at high conversion levels.

Materials and Methods

Preparation of Catalysts :

In the preparation of catalysts, a novel technique has been adopted. The active components of the catalyst were formulated as an uniform mix by fusion and subsequently deposited on supports such as silica gel, from its aqueous solution followed by heating to decompose the salts to the active oxides. The process is covered by an Indian patent⁶.

Feed Material :

Anthracene of 94% purity was used as feed for the study.

Experimental set up

It consisted of an air blower, anthracene feeder, air preheater and the reactor, followed by air condensers and water scrubbers. The details of the set up used for fluid bed studies were described in an earlier paper³. The catalysts used were of size range -36, +100 mesh B.S.S.

Analysis of Products :

Anthraquinone was estimated by reducing the product with sodium hydrosulphite to soluble anthrahydroquinone which was filtered free of unreacted anthracene and then regenerated to anthraquinone by sodium peroxide.

Phthalic and maleic anhydrides were estimated by titrating the hot water extract of the product of oxidation with standard solutions of alkali and potassium permanganate. The details of the methods were fully discussed in an earlier paper³.

In the case of some experiments anthracene and anthraquinone were estimated by rapid Gas Chromatographic method developed at this Institute⁷.

Results and Discussion

The work done at this Institute had shown that catalysts prepared in a particular manner by fusing vanadium oxide with normal or acidic alkali metal salts alone or in presence of H_2SO_4 were effective for the oxidation of anthracene to anthraquinone. The procedure disclosed in our patent⁶, enabled the active catalyst components to be obtained as a homogeneous mixture, suitable quantities of which could be deposited from its solution on silica gel support.

Throughout this paper the term contact time signifies the ratio of fluidized volume of the catalyst to the total volume of gaseous mixture passing over the catalyst at reaction temperature per unit time

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and the space velocity of feed means the weight of feed per unit time per unit volume of catalyst. In all the experiments the space velocity of air was maintained at 5333 litres at NTP per hour per litre of catalyst.

Fig. 1 shows the results obtained for various loading of the active components on silica gel support. In these studies, the molar ratio of the vanadium oxide to potassium oxide was maintained at 1 : 2.5. All these experiments were done at around the optimum temperature range.

Fig. 1. Effect of Variation of V_2O_5 -content of the Catalyst.

- 1.0 mole V_2O_5 per kg. silica gel
- ⊗—1.2 " " " " " "
- ×—1.4 " " " " " "
- △—1.6 " " " " " "

It is observed that higher conversions were obtained when air/feed ratio was above 40. Lower ratios resulted in lower conversions of anthracene. It was interesting to note, however, that increasing the air/feed ratio did not result in further oxidation of the anthraquinone first formed to any great extent, indicating the high selectivity of the catalyst for anthraquinone.

The results distinctly indicate that catalysts composition containing 1.4 moles of V_2O_5 gave the best results, higher V_2O_5 contents resulting in lower conversions to anthraquinone.

Fig. 2 shows the results of experiments in which the $V_2O_5 : K_2O$ molar ratio was varied from 1 : 2.5 to 1 : 4 keeping the V_2O_5 loading at 1 mole per Kg of silica gel. The superiority of the catalyst having the higher ratio of K_2O is distinctly shown.

Fig. 2. Effect of Variation of $V_2O_5 : K_2O$ Ratio in the Catalyst.

- ⊗— $V_2O_5 : K_2O : : 1 : 2.5$
- $V_2O_5 : K_2O : : 1 : 4.0$

Fig. 2 also shows that the higher K_2O ratio enabled conversions to anthraquinone of over 92% to be obtained, a level which could be achieved only with catalysts containing over 1.4 moles of V_2O_5 per Kg of silica gel support (Fig. 1). This means that the cost of the catalyst could be brought down to a considerable extent consequent on the reduction of V_2O_5 loading. All subsequent experiments were done keeping the $V_2O_5 : K_2O$ ratio at 1 : 4.

It is seen from Fig. 3 that the catalyst gave conversions to anthraquinone of over 92% in the temperature range 330-390° and over 90% in the range 325-405° which shows good flexibility in operation. This is a desirable characteristic as significant variation in catalyst temperature during operation in a commercial reactor would not bring down the conversions drastically.

Fig. 3. Effect of Variation of Catalyst Temperature.

Fig. 4 shows the variation of space velocity of anthracene feed over a wide range. All these experiments were done in the temperature range 340-360° where the conversions to anthraquinone were in the range 93-95%. Conversions to anthraquinone of 94% and over (weight yield of anthraquinone of over 110% on the basis of anthracene feed) could be obtained at space velocity of 90-200 gms of anthracene feed per hour per litre of catalyst at contact time in the order of 0.3-0.4 seconds, which again shows good flexibility from the point of view of operation of larger reactor.

Fig. 4. Effect of Variation of Anthracene Feed Rate, (Catalyst Temperature - 340-360°).

The optimum conditions for fluid bed operation with the catalyst are shown in Table 1.

TABLE I—OPTIMUM CONDITIONS FOR FLUID BED OPERATIONS

<i>Catalyst</i>	
Size range (B.S.S.)	- 36, +100
Bulk density (g/c.c)	0.94.
<i>Experimental Conditions</i>	
Space Velocity of feed (g/hr/lit catalyst)	180-200
Space Velocity of air (Lit/hr/lit catalyst at NTP)	5333
Reaction temperature, °C	840-980
Contact time, Second, (at reaction temperature)	0.3-0.4
Air/Feed ratio (W/W)	30-40
<i>Conversion and Yield</i>	
Conversion of anthracene to anthraquinone, %	92-94
Weight yield of anthraquinone (on anthracene basis), %	108-111
Space time yield of anthraquinone (gram. anthraquinone produced/hr/lit catalyst)	195-220
<i>Analysis of Product</i>	
1. <i>Crude Product</i>	
Anthraquinone, %	93-95
Anthracene, %	<1
Phthalic anhydride, %	4-6
Maleic anhydride, %	<1
2. <i>Purified Product</i>	
(After water extraction)	
Anthraquinone, %	>99
Anthracene, %	<1

The high selectivity to anthraquinone permits the suggestion that the possible over all scheme of reactions is same as that reported earlier^{1,2} and that the relative rates of the various reactions would also be similar.

Purification of the Products of Oxidation :

The impurities present in the oxidation products namely phthalic anhydride and maleic anhydride could be easily removed by extraction with hot water. As shown in Table 1, it was possible to obtain anthraquinone of over 99% purity by this method. Anthraquinone of this level of purity is quite suitable for further processing for dyestuffs manufacture.

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